

Workshop Report:

RDMO for Editors – 13. & 14. November 2025

The Basic Service DMP4NFDI held the hands-on online workshop "RDMO for Editors" on 13 and 14 November. The workshop was based on the newly developed Train-the-Trainer concept for DMPs and RDMO¹, and marked the first test of the Advanced Level of the RDMO module. This level focuses on hands-on usage and familiarisation with the RDMO interface from an editor's perspective as well as working with the NFDI DMP Template Framework². The modular format allowed attendees to join either the introductory session on Day 1 or the more specialised session on Day 2, in sum seven hours of training.

The first day focused on providing a foundation in catalog creation within RDMO. This session required no previous experience, allowing newcomers to become familiar with the essential elements and capabilities of RDMO. Through guided exercises, participants learned how to build a catalog from scratch with structured sections, pages and questions while familiarising themselves with the RDMO editor's interface. The second day built upon these fundamentals and introduced additional RDMO components, such as Collections and Conditions, as well as the NFDI DMP Template Framework which was provided as a template in RDMO. This template is designed to support the creation of interoperable and standardised catalogs in NFDI.

The gathered feedback highlighted RDMO as a powerful and useful tool, because templates can be adapted to institutional or discipline-specific needs and it allows the reuse of existing templates. At the same time, several participants described the tool as initially confusing or complex, particularly when working with specific components such as Attributes and Conditions. Participants expressed interest in covering these topics in greater depth in future workshops. Regarding the workshop structure, the alternation between theory and practice, the breakout rooms and the trainers' guidance were received positively across both days. Despite the initial difficulties with the tool, participants emphasized that the workshop instructions and hands-on guidance helped them navigate the tool effectively.

¹ Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771036>

² Schönau, S., Windeck, J., Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Wallace, D., Castro, L. J., Diederichs, K., & Schmitz, D. (2025). The NFDI DMP Template Framework (1-0-0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737079>

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